

RESEARCH OF THE TRANSPORTATION CAPACITY OF THE CITY STREET ROAD NETWORK (ON THE EXAMPLE OF THE CITY OF URGENCH)

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Abstract. *In this article, an experimental study was conducted to increase the capacity of the road network in the city of Urgench, where the population is growing. The intersection of “Pahlavon Mahmud” and “Tinchlik” streets, one of the busiest intersections in the city, was selected as the research object. The study results were analyzed, and recommendations were proposed to enhance the intersection’s capacity.*

Аннотация: *В статье представлено экспериментальное исследование по увеличению пропускной способности дорожной сети в быстрорастущем городе Ургенч. В качестве объекта исследования был выбран перекресток улиц «Рахлавон Махмуд» и «Тинчлик», один из трехполосных перекрестков города. По результатам исследования были проанализированы и даны предложения и рекомендации по увеличению пропускной способности перекрестка.*

Keywords: *transport, city streets, traffic congestion, traffic intensity, intersection, traffic flow, carrying capacity*

Ключевые слова: *транспорт, городские улицы, загруженность дорог, интенсивность движения, перекресток, транспортный поток, проницаемость*

Introduction: The increasing number of motor vehicles not only causes significant harm to the environment and society but also leads to several inconveniences. Taking Urgench city as an example, the growing traffic flow has led to congestion, prolonged vehicle waiting times at intersections, disruption of movement schedules, delays for residents reaching service centers, and an increase in traffic accidents. These have become pressing issues in the city. Therefore, increasing the capacity of urban streets has become one of the most critical and urgent challenges today. In order to comprehensively consider existing problems and further improve the road safety system in the Republic of Uzbekistan, radically improve the road infrastructure, increase the quality of roads, as well as create the necessary conditions for the safe movement of all road users, legislative acts are being developed: Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated December 9, 2019 Year. PD-5890 “On measures for the deep reform of the road system of the Republic of Uzbekistan”[1], Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan, 09.12.2019 y. № DP-4545 Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan “On measures to further improve the road management system” and other regulatory legal acts related to this activity, one of the urgent tasks is to study the capacity of the road network.[2]

Main part: When determining the capacity of urban roads, it is first necessary to have information about the main indicators characterizing traffic flows. In this research work, we analyze the main indicators of traffic flows.[3]

1. **Traffic intensity**-this is the total number of vehicles passing a certain section of the road per unit of time. Often, 1 hour or 1 day is taken as the time interval, and the traffic intensity is determined in vehicles/hour or vehicles/day, respectively. To solve the problem of traffic organization, data on the hourly and average annual traffic intensity are used. This indicator is determined by observation or by automatic methods.

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2. **Visual (observation) method**-the speed of movement on a certain section of the road is calculated using a special blank, which records the number of vehicles passing per unit of time (minute, hour, day).

3. **Traffic composition**-is determined by the share of a particular type of transport in units or percentages in relation to the entire traffic flow.

For example, the traffic flow in urban streets is characterized by the following indicators: passenger cars 85÷92%; buses 3÷6%; trolleybuses 0.1÷0.3%; trucks 4÷9%.

This article presents the results of an experimental study of the traffic intensity of motor vehicles at the intersection of “Pahlavon Mahmud” and “Tinchlik” streets in Urgench. The reason for choosing this intersection as a research object is that it is one of the central streets of the city, where there is a central farmers' market, Amir Temur Park, banks, shops, and several places visited by residents.

Traffic flow measurements were conducted during peak hours on working days, specifically from 8:30 to 9:30, 12:30 to 13:30, and 17:30 to 18:30.

Diagram 1.0. Number of vehicles passing through "Pahlavon Mahmud" Street from 08:30 to 09:30.

Diagram 1.0 shows that at "Pahlavon Mahmud" Street, the highest number of vehicles 724 passenger cars, was recorded between 9:00 and 9:15, because this is the start of working and school hours.

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Diagram 1.1. Number of vehicles passing through "Tinchlik" Street from 08:30 to 09:30.

Diagram 2.1. Number of vehicles passing through "Pahlavon Mahmud" Street from 12:30 to 13:30. As we can see from Diagram 2.1 indicates that the highest traffic volume, 742 vehicles, was recorded between 13:00 and 13:15.

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Diagram 2.2. Number of vehicles passing through "Tinchlik" Street from 12:30 to 13:30.

Diagram 3.1. Number of vehicles passing through "Pahlavon Mahmud" Street from 17:30 to 18:30.

Diagrams 3.1 and 3.2 show that the number of vehicles decreased during the 17:30 to 18:30 period at "Pahlavon Mahmud" and "Tinchlik" streets.

Diagram 3.2. Number of vehicles passing through "Tinchlik" Street from 17:30 to 18:30.

The theoretical throughput capacity of the intersection at "Pahlavon Mahmud" and "Tinchlik" streets was determined using the following formula:

$$N_{np} = \sum_{i=1}^m (N_i k_{npi}) \quad (1)$$

where: N_i – traffic intensity on a single lane; k_{npi} - reduction coefficient for each type of vehicle; m - number of vehicle types considered in the observations.

To calculate traffic intensity, various vehicle types were converted to equivalent passenger car units using specific coefficients [Table 1]. At the intersection of "Tinchlik" and "Pahlavon Mahmud" streets, one of the busiest intersections in the city of Urgench, work was calculate on SHNQ. 2.07.01-23 to determine traffic intensity using natural observations.[5]

[Table 1]

Types of transportation	Coefficients
Light car	1.0
Bus	2.5
Trucks up to 2 tons	1.5
Truck 2-5 tons	2.0
Truck 5-8 tons	2.5
Truck over 8 tons	3.5
Trolleybus	3.0
Motorcycle, bicycle	0.5

Using these coefficients, a conditional cartogram of the intersection's traffic intensity at "Pahlavon Mahmud" and "Tinchlik" streets was developed for the period from 12:30 to 13:30 [1-photo].

1-photo. Conditional cartogram of traffic intensity at "Pahlavon Mahmud" and "Tinchlik" intersection.

The study revealed that the highest hourly traffic volume occurred between 12:30 and 13:30. Knowing the number of vehicles passing through the intersection, we calculated the daily and annual average traffic intensity using the following formula: N. (1)

$$N = N_{np} K_M K_H K_C \quad (1)$$

Here K_M, K_H, K_C - monthly, weekly and daily adjustment coefficients. Average annual, daily traffic intensity values are presented in Table 2 below.

Table 2.

Type of cars	N_{np}	Coefficients			N
		K_M	K_H	K_C	
Light car	4488	1.32	0.89	8.47	47932
Truck	81				865
Bus	159				1698
Total	4728				50495

At the highest traffic intensity ($N_{tv} = 801$ vehicles/hour), we define the actual capacity of the intersection as $801 * 10 = 8010$ vehicles/hour. The actual traffic intensity is equal to the sum of traffic intensities over ten time intervals: $\sum i N_{\phi} = 8010$ vehicles/hour. Thus,

$$Z = 6488/8010 = 0.81. \quad (2)$$

According to the movement intensity of motor vehicles, this section operates within the permitted limits. Now, let's analyze the conflict points at the "Pahlavon Mahmud" – "Tinchlik" intersection.

$$m = n_0 + 3n_c + 5n_n, \quad (3)$$

where: n_0, n_c, n_n , represent the number of deviations, merging points, and crossing points, respectively. The complexity of an intersection can be classified as follows:

- $m < 40 \rightarrow$ low complexity (simple),
- $40 \leq m < 80 \rightarrow$ medium complexity,
- $80 \leq m < 150 \rightarrow$ high complexity,
- $m > 150 \rightarrow$ very high complexity.

By calculating the complexity using formula (3):

$$m=8+8*3+16*5=112$$

Since $m=112>80$, we can conclude that the complexity level of the "Pahlavon Mahmud" – "Tinchlik" intersection is high.

Conclusion: Based on the experimental research on one of the most congested intersections in Urgench city, the "Tinchlik" and "Pahlavon Mahmud" streets' intersection has been proven to have a high complexity level of traffic congestion.

To improve the intersection's capacity, the construction of an overpass is recommended. Implementing an overpass will increase the intersection's throughput capacity, enhance traffic safety, save residents' time, and reduce the harmful gas emissions from vehicles caused by traffic congestion.

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